

"Ectoparasites found in domestic cats"

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Abstract: This scientific work focuses on the types of ectoparasites—external parasites (lice, fleas)—commonly found in cats, their biological characteristics, their negative impact on the feline body, as well as prevention and treatment measures. The study identified the most frequently encountered ectoparasites as *Ctenocephalides felis* (cat flea), *Notoedres cati*—a parasite responsible for causing sarcoptic mange in cats, and *Pulex irritans*. These parasites can cause itching, allergic reactions, skin inflammation, and secondary infections in cats.

Keywords: Ectoparasite, *Ctenocephalides felis*, *Notoedres cati*, *Pulex irritans*, *felis cats*

Introduction. the increasing number of domestic animals, particularly cats, has led to a rise in ectoparasitic diseases among them. This scientific work focuses on the main ectoparasites found in cats — fleas (*Ctenocephalides felis*), ticks (*Ixodes spp.*), ear mites (*Otodectes cynotis*), and other external parasites — exploring their biology, impact on the feline body, pathogenic potential, and treatment methods. The study also examines the threats these parasites pose to cat health, their immune systems, and their potential transmission to humans. Preventive measures, modern antiparasitic treatments, and veterinary approaches are analyzed in detail. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of how to combat ectoparasites in cats and their role in the ecological environment.

Notoedres cati belongs to the same family as the parasites that cause sarcoptic mange in cats. This disease occurs in both domestic and wild cats worldwide, with the highest number of cases reported in Europe, India, and North America. As previously mentioned, this condition is caused by extremely small mites known as *Notoedres cati*. These parasites are microscopic and cannot be seen with the naked eye; their size is approximately 0.2×0.25 mm. Adult mites have a round shape, are gray in color, and have short legs.

Нотоэдроз

Adult mites mate within small depressions on the epidermis (the surface layer of the skin), after which the females lay eggs in the deeper layers of the skin. Larvae hatch from the eggs and gradually develop into adult parasites, eventually migrating to the surface of the skin. The life cycle of these parasites lasts approximately three weeks. The parasite cannot survive for long without a host (i.e., outside the animal's body); its survival depends on environmental temperature and humidity.

Mites spread very quickly; therefore, if they are detected in one adult cat or in one kitten among a group, there is a high likelihood that the others have also been infected.

Notoedrosis affects the health and condition of cats in various ways—it can lead to extensive damage to skin tissues, allergic reactions, weakened immunity, secondary bacterial infections, and other complications. Initially, the mites affect the skin of the head, ears, and neck. The disease must be treated, as failure to do so may result in severe consequences. With timely and proper treatment, the chances of recovery are high. Clinical signs of the disease typically appear within one month after infestation.

The spread of parasites is also facilitated by factors such as the overcrowded housing of cats, close physical contact, frequent outdoor exposure, and poor hygiene practices. The disease can be easily transmitted from mother to offspring, and often the entire litter becomes infected at the same time.

In cases of notoedrosis in cats, intense itching occurs, leading to skin thickening, wrinkling, and hair loss. The affected animal may also develop a rash consisting of small red bumps and vesicles in certain areas. Initially, the infestation is localized, but it gradually spreads and forms crusts (dry scabs). The most commonly affected areas are the head, ear margins, neck, and lower parts of the limbs.

Scratches caused by intense itching often lead to secondary bacterial infections. If notoedrosis is not treated promptly and the disease progresses, it can spread throughout the entire body. In such cases, the animal's appetite decreases, it loses weight, and experiences significant pain.

Fleas belonging to the genus *Ctenocephalides felis* are found worldwide on dogs and cats. They also infest many other species of mammals.

Life cycle of fleas: Adult fleas live on the host's fur and feed on their blood. They lay eggs in the fur, which then fall to the ground. Flea larvae hatch from the eggs. The larvae then develop into pupae, within which immature fleas develop. In this stage, they can survive in the environment for several months.

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In response to certain external stimuli—such as heat, pressure (e.g., the host's movement), and carbon dioxide (the gas exhaled by the host)—the pupa breaks open, releasing the young flea. This flea must quickly find a new host.

Clinical signs: The primary clinical signs of flea infestations are itching and redness. If the flea population is very high, this can lead to blood loss (anemia). In some dogs (and less commonly in cats), a severe allergic reaction to substances in flea saliva develops, resulting in significant skin damage. This condition is known as flea allergy dermatitis (FAD). In such animals, fleas can sometimes be difficult to detect because, despite the severe symptoms, the fleas remain hidden.

Pulex irritans (the human flea) delivers painful bites that cause sores on the host's body and serves as a carrier for various species of *Bartonella* bacteria. These bacteria can cause trench fever, while species of *Rickettsia* are responsible for diseases such as Rocky Mountain spotted fever and Mediterranean spotted fever. To investigate the hosts, distribution, and molecular characteristics of this flea species, we conducted a study in Meshkin-Shahr district, Ardabil province, located in northwestern Iran.

Pulex irritans is an obligate hematophagous (blood-feeding) ectoparasite of both humans and animals. Therefore, considering its relatively high occurrence on cats and dogs, it is recommended to conduct in-depth studies on its distribution and its potential role as a vector of pathogenic agents between these animals and humans. The results of such research can be used to develop and improve control programs targeting this vector.

"As the name suggests, this species does not have a specific host and can feed on the blood of a wide range of mammals. This trait makes it a vector of various diseases — for example, it can transmit illnesses such as *Dipylidium caninum* and trench fever. In addition, *Rickettsia* species can cause Rocky Mountain spotted fever and Mediterranean spotted fever."

Conclusion: Studying ectoparasitic infestations in domestic cats is of great importance not only for protecting animal health but also for safeguarding human health, preventing epizootic and epidemic

situations, and advancing veterinary practice. Strengthening research and preventive measures in this field is considered one of the urgent tasks.

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